

**SOCIAL AND PEDAGOGICAL FACTORS FOR ENSURING THE SUCCESS OF
STUDENTS IN EDUCATION (USING THE EXAMPLE OF INTERNATIONAL
ASSESSMENT STUDIES)**

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Abstract: The article analyzes the socio-pedagogical factors of ensuring the success of students in education. Scientific analysis is based on the example of international evaluation studies.

Key words: educational success, socio-pedagogical factors, educational content, international evaluation studies

Introduction. The relevance of socio-pedagogical tasks such as improving the content of national education, reforming school education, preparing students for independent life, and forming the skills necessary for their success is increasing. For this, from a pedagogical point of view, it is necessary to carry out reforms to improve curricula, textbooks, teaching methods, and the system for assessing educational results based on modern requirements, while from a social point of view, issues such as increasing the importance of the family institution in ensuring students' educational success, strengthening school-family cooperation, and social equality in education are gaining relevance.

Results and Discussion. Education is not just a process of teaching students something, but also of providing them with the necessary opportunities to move confidently and quickly in an increasingly complex and changing world [12.27]. In order to improve the quality and efficiency of education, it is of urgent importance to study foreign best practices, introduce international standards, conduct a comparative analysis of the existing system, and improve the national assessment system that meets the requirements of the time [11. 21].

In general secondary schools, attention is being paid to raising the intellectual development of students to a qualitatively new level by adapting the content of education to the requirements of the international assessment programs of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development – OECD) (Progress in International Reading and Literacy Study – PIRLS), Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study – TIMSS), The Programme for International Student Assessment – PISA), The Teaching and Learning International Survey – TALIS) [7. 4]. Achieving educational effectiveness through combining the potential of educational subjects, implementing modern pedagogical approaches in general secondary education, and studying the socio-pedagogical factors of students' success in education is of great importance.

Leading scientific centers and scientists of the world are conducting fundamental and applied research on the socio-pedagogical foundations of the implementation of international assessment studies in the national education system. Today, the implementation of international assessment studies in the national education system in our republic and, through this, the formation of basic competencies in students, the development of life-practical skills necessary for their success, and their preparation for the political, socio-economic life of society are noted as the ultimate goal of the reforms being implemented in the field of education. For this, international experiences are being studied and gradually implemented in the field of education, which form the content of the national education system: curricula, textbooks, teaching methodologies and the system for assessing educational results, based on modern requirements. On the other hand, ensuring that students receive quality education in accordance with the principle of social equality in education and thereby prepare them for independent life, as well as developing decision-making, creative and critical thinking competencies, is considered one of the main areas of reform.

International assessment studies are organized at the initiative of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD). The purpose of the studies is to assess the level of preparation of students for future political, economic, and social life and to forecast the human capital being formed. Based on this, assessment studies have a specific methodological approach. The tasks used in the studies and the questionnaires provided to school management, teachers, students and their parents are aimed at determining not only the student's knowledge of a particular subject, but also the ability to apply the acquired knowledge in independent life, the level of their preparation for socio-economic relations, and the acquisition of competencies that meet the requirements of society.

Scientific and practical research on determining students' educational achievements and their international comparison is carried out by a number of world organizations and higher education institutions, including the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA), the Netherlands National Institute for Educational Measurement (CITO) (Netherlands), the Educational Testing Service (ETS) (USA), the National Institute for Educational Research (NIER) (Japan), the Technical University of Munich (Germany), the Institute for Educational Development Strategies of the Russian Academy of Education (ISRO RAO) (Russia), the National Center for Educational Statistics and Evaluation under the Ministry of Education and Science of the Republic of Kazakhstan (Kazakhstan) [13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20,21] being carried out by institutions.

International assessment studies determine the current and necessary state of socio-economic development and human capital development by linking the level of formation of basic competencies in students of general education institutions to the socio-pedagogical aspects of their education. The effectiveness of the implementation of international experiences in pedagogical practice into the national education system is inextricably linked with the study of social development trends in society and the planning of educational reforms taking these aspects into account.

In international assessment studies, the social aspects of ensuring the success of students in education are assessed on the basis of scientifically based criteria. These criteria include:

- the social background of the student;
- the understanding of the importance of education in one's life;
- the effectiveness of the "general education institution-family cooperation mechanism";
- the development of educational values in families;
- the availability and current state of use of social, academic and cultural resources[6. 24].

The TIMSS International Assessment Study is the world's longest-running program to measure student achievement in mathematics and science.[4. 16] The study is administered by the TIMSS and PIRLS International Center for Learning at Boston College. Since 1995, TIMSS has been tracking trends in mathematics and science achievement around the world, providing high-quality data that policymakers and education professionals use to make evidence-based decisions about education systems and programs.[9. 21] In addition to measuring the reading comprehension of primary school students, PIRLS also serves as a powerful tool to provide information about the environments in which students learn to read at home and at school. Decades of research in education, including the results of the four PIRLS assessment cycles, show that the scope of learning opportunities and the learning environment for students significantly affect their learning outcomes, creating an environment that provides more opportunities and comprehensive support for them to demonstrate high levels of achievement. The extensive data collected in each of the PIRLS assessments conducted to date (2001, 2006, 2011, and 2016) on the development of students' reading comprehension skills in and out of school, the comparative analysis of factors related to the educational process and students' results in different years in the PIRLS international study, and the high-level assessment of students' reading achievement have served as the basis for conducting research on how to improve their reading and learning. Taking into account the results of the PIRLS assessment program that has now been conducted, the changes in students' achievement indicators serve as convincing evidence of whether the reforms or practical measures implemented in the education sector are effective or not

in accordance with the approaches adopted in this regard[10. 18].

A number of studies, including the PIRLS program, have shown that parents' early literacy activities are crucial for children's higher reading achievement. Examples of these activities include reading, storytelling, playing with alphabet toys, interacting with other children, helping children write letters and words, and saying signs and symbols out loud.[2. 16] The PIRLS international program collects information about school-related factors in the learning process. These include the availability of educational materials specifically designed for learning, the school's learning environment, the level of safety and order in the school, and the school's focus on developing reading skills. Adequate working conditions, facilities, and learning materials are essential for creating a conducive learning environment in schools.[5. 56]

National and school-level reforms determine curricula. The extent to which national curricula are implemented in schools is reflected in the curriculum developed at the school level. In each assessment cycle, PIRLS asks school principals about the reading curriculum taught in primary schools and the focus of their schools on developing specific reading skills and strategies. These skills range from students' ability to recognize the letters of the alphabet to more complex skills such as identifying the author's worldview or purpose. Encouraging students to read from a young age is important for teachers of reading because students who are motivated to read are more likely to develop good reading skills. According to the theory of self-actualization, students can be motivated by creating a conducive environment that fosters a sense of belonging, competition, and freedom in the student. An overly controlled classroom environment can be a stumbling block to student motivation because it robs students of their sense of freedom. One way teachers can help students develop independent reading skills is by providing students with texts that interest them. In addition, the relationship between the teacher and the student is important in motivating students. In the PIRLS program, teachers are asked about the variety of activities they provide to motivate students, the time they are given to read a text or material of their choice, and the encouragement they give to students to discuss the text[3. 25].

Functional changes in the content of education, such as assessing students' skills such as "the ability to apply the acquired knowledge in practice, critical thinking and analysis of the given material"[1], require a radical change and intensification of students' learning activities not only in a general secondary educational institution, but also in society and in the family.

Books and book reading play a great role in the formation of the educational environment in the family. Analysis of scientific literature A positive attitude towards books in the family is reflected in the cognitive development of children in the following ways:

- helps to understand the environment, the world and oneself;
- develops the ability to remember and think. That is, a person who reads a lot of books has a good level of memory, thinks quickly and draws conclusions quickly;
- directs them to interpretation, analysis and the formation of personal opinion;
- is the basis for many achievements and successes;
- teaches how to interact with people correctly and forms correct speech;
- increases vocabulary and literacy;
- reveals hidden creative abilities in children.

International assessment studies assess the development of basic and subject-specific competencies of secondary school students. An analysis of the scientific literature shows that all secondary school subjects simultaneously aim to develop subject-specific and basic competencies. These two competencies have a "network" character, complement each other and are interconnected. The term "literacy" is used in the PISA international assessment program, which corresponds to the Uzbek term "savodkhonlik". This term refers to a set of basic competencies that determine a student's readiness for social life[8. 266]. The term "literacy" does not refer to competencies formed within a specific subject, but to competencies necessary for a student to find his or her place in society, establish a professional career, possess personal development skills, develop an appropriate attitude

towards society, political, economic, social life, technology, and to assume roles such as "active citizen", "high-level consumer", and "rational user of the environment and resources".

The socio-pedagogical necessity of applying international evaluation studies to the national education system is reflected in the following:

Comparability: Countries participating in international evaluation studies will have the opportunity to compare their national education with that of other countries. This will provide valuable information about the strengths and weaknesses of the national education system and identify areas for improving the education system.

Exchange of best practices: By comparing the national education system with other countries, it will be possible to study the best practices implemented in practice and implement them based on the characteristics of the national education system.

Acceleration of reforms: The results of international evaluation studies will help those responsible for education policy to accelerate the activities of education policymakers to accelerate educational reforms, and speed up the decision-making process for fundamental changes in the education sector. In particular, it aims to improve the quality of education, support equality in education, and pursue socio-pedagogical goals.

Access to scientific and empirical data: Participation in international evaluation studies provides an opportunity to familiarize oneself with scientific and theoretical data on the state of implementation of the results of pedagogical scientific research in other countries. Scientific and comparative analyses serve as an important impetus for the formation of new scientific projects in the national education system.

Transparency and accountability: Participation in international evaluation studies requires participating countries to consider transparency and accountability as an obligation. In this regard, the results are presented openly and transparently to the general public. This creates a convenient opportunity to study the public's opinion on the existing education system.

Conclusions. The implementation of international assessment studies in the national education system is a socio-pedagogical necessity in terms of social equality, quality of education, the introduction of innovations in the social sphere into the education system, and the promotion of evidence-based decision-making. The socio-pedagogical aspects of the implementation of international assessment studies in the national education system are as follows:

Social equality: The results of international assessment studies provide an opportunity to assess the real state of social equality on the basis of the national education system by comparing the education systems of the participating countries. In particular, they allow comparing the differences between girls and boys, students in urban and rural schools, and those who are financially well-off and those who are less well-off. The results of the study serve to form ideas for the implementation of best practices and innovative approaches in the field of social equality, taking into account national educational development trends and national characteristics. This helps to address social inequalities in education and create equal educational opportunities for all students.

Ensuring the quality of education: International evaluation studies provide an understanding of best practices and indicate what measures can be taken to improve the quality of education. This allows the national education system to set quality standards and serve as a basis for continuous improvement.

Social innovation: Sharing information on the best practices and pedagogical practices of other countries leads to the stimulation of social innovation in the national education system. This includes the integration of new teaching methods, pedagogical approaches and new technologies to improve the learning process and meet the needs of students. It also leads to the formation of new types of activities in the cooperation of secondary schools with parents, social organizations.

Decision-making on social issues in education: The results of international evaluation studies serve as a basis for making policy decisions based on scientific evidence in the field of education. They help to objectively assess the effectiveness of educational reforms, take into account social

factors in ensuring educational effectiveness, allocate resources, and make informed decisions about the sustainability and future of the education sector. The results of international evaluation studies and their scientific analysis in different countries clearly show that the social background of students is closely related to their educational success, and that the effectiveness of the national education system requires taking into account its social aspects and constantly studying social issues along with problems related to the education system. The causes of social inequality in education are diverse and complex. Educational policy in the field of the national education system is important in solving such social issues, but it cannot be the only solution to solve all social problems. Social issues related to education are being addressed by studying issues such as the cooperation of secondary schools with other institutions of society, the training and development of teachers, the distribution of economic resources in society and the financing of education, and the raising of the importance of education to the level of values. Ministries and departments in the field of education should not be considered as the only institution that can solve all educational problems.

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